

E-Governance

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Introduction

The foremost step in e-governance is to describe governance. ‘Governance’ is a problematic term; it is hardly an exaggeration to explain the word as close to anarchical, the literature suggesting that definitions of governance, if not incompatible, are often a long way apart. The use of ICT to support public services, democracy, the private sector, etc.;

- Technology-mediated services
- Something that includes e-government
- A model of government
- A commitment to technology
- Functions that empower citizens
- Internally focused use of ICT by government
- About networks and relationships
- Use of ICT to improve the quality services and governance
- Something that enhances e-democracy
- A technology-mediated relationship between citizen and state.

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Government and Governance

Government is the body of representatives that governs and controls the state at a given time. Government is the medium through which the power of the state is employed.

Governance is the act of governing or ruling. It is the set of rules and laws framed by the government that are to be implemented through the representatives of the state. Simply put, governance is what governments do.

Structural E-Governance

“E-Governance” consists of the structures, leadership, and processes that allow an organization to make good decisions to ensure that its IT sustains and extends its strategies and targets.

Structurally, from a government perspective, there are three/four state organizations involved:

- The local authority;
- The planning department;
- The Council;
- The applicant;
- The objectors;
- The builder;
- The architects;

There is a clear process for which it is worth setting out the key steps:

1. The applicant can prepare and finish the essential documentation;
2. The applicant can inform the planners and the society about his application;
3. The planners can make all applicable information available to all involved citizens;
4. Interested party can express their views to the planners and entity if they wish;
5. The planners are required to take account of all views submitted as well as the law and planning guidelines;

Normative E-Governance

The IIAS definition of e-government suggests that while the concept of governance does not necessarily have to have a normative connotation, it generally does so in practice and that this was not unreasonable. The idea of ‘good’ government is a powerful one. The history of government and public administration contains numerous examples Of failures of public governance

In approximate order of importance these

- The Legal provisions;
- Process;
- Government;
- Power;
- Individual psychology;
- Organizational psychology;
- Mechanics.

Virtual Organization

Most misused terms in information systems are ‘virtual organization’. By this is usually meant an organization that does not occupy a bodily office or building, but where real people communicate automatically from wherever they are. Such an organization is not virtual in the proper sense of that term. However, technology may now, be taking us in the direction of the genuinely virtual organization.

Conclusion

ICTs only enable the transformation, they do not create it and hence the social and political norms in any areas will determine the outcome of the ‘e-governance’ systems. We need to develop more stylish systems for capturing and measure the impact of e-governance so that we can judge its achievement in other than just crude, ‘availability’ terms. And we need to be able to judge the real contact on citizens, not just changes in making or division of public services.

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